

Syntaxonomy of Chilean Vegetation

M. Alvarez and F. Luebert

Alvarez M. & Luebert F. (2022). Chilean vegetation in the context of the Braun-Blanquet approach and a comparison with EcoVeg formations. Vegetation Classification and Survey. doi: [10.3897/VCS.72194](https://doi.org/10.3897/VCS.72194)

Hierarchical relationships between syntaxa recorded for the Chilean vegetation. Syntaxonomic ranks are recognized by their indentation and by their suffixes, as stated in the Art. 11 of the **International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature** (see [Theurillat et al., 2020](#)). The names of the classes (highest syntaxonomic ranks) are formatted in bold fonts.

Synonyms are placed below their respective accepted names and are indicated by a leading equal symbol. Besides every accepted name a link to the respective syntaxonomic view is added after the abbreviation sec. (*secundum*), which corresponds to the publication used as reference defining the circumscriptions of the respective syntaxonomic concepts. These terms are applied in analogous to plant taxonomy (see [Alvarez & Luebert, 2018](#) for a glossary).

Ambrosietea chamissonis Kohler 1970 sec. Kohler ([1970](#))

Ambrosietalia chamissonis Kohler 1970 sec. Kohler ([1970](#))

Polygonion sanguinariae Kohler 1970 sec. Kohler ([1970](#))

Poo cumingii-Ambrosietum chamissonis Kohler 1970 sec. Kohler ([1970](#))

Anthochloo lepidulae-Dielsiochloetea floribundae Rivas-Martínez & Tovar 1982 sec. Luebert and Gajardo ([2005](#))

Anthochloo lepidulae-Dielsiochloetalia floribundae Rivas-Martínez & Tovar 1982 sec. Luebert and Gajardo ([2005](#))

Wernerio ciliollatae-Englerocharion peruviana Rivas-Martínez & Tovar 1982 sec. Luebert and Gajardo ([2005](#))

Wernerion dactylophyllae Gutte 1987 sec. Luebert and Gajardo ([2005](#))

Nototrichion obcuneatae Galán de Mera, Cáceres & González 2003 sec. Luebert and Gajardo ([2005](#))

Chaetantherion sphaeroidalis Galán de Mera, Cáceres & González 2003 sec. Luebert and Gajardo ([2005](#))

Senecionion zoellneri-scorzoneræfolii Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Senecioni zoellneri-Azorelletum compactae Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Wernerion pseudodigitatae Ruthsatz 1977 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Nototricho auricomae-Chaetantheretum sphaeroidalis Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)

Bidentetea tripartiti Tüxen et al. ex von Rochow 1951 sec. Mucina (1997)

Bidentetalia tripartiti Braun-Blanquet et Tüxen 1943 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

alliance?

Polypogo australis-Polygonetum hydropiperi Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Deschampsio-Asteretea vahlii Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Deschampsio-Asteretalia vahlii Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Deschampsio-Asterion vahlii Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Plantago barbatae-Deschampsietum laxae Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Apio australis-Senecionetum smithii Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Alopecuro magellanicum-Caricetum darwinii Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Deschampsietum kingii Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Arenario serpentis-Seneciotalia philippii Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Arenario serpentis-Senecion philippii Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Arenario serpentis-Agrophyretum magellanicum Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Luzulo racemosae-Ourisietum ruelloidis Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Empetro rubrum-Pernettyetea Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Pernettyetalia Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Baccharido umbelliformis-Pernettyion poeppigii Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Baccharido umbelliformis-Pernettyetum poeppigii Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Leucomyrtillo-Pernettyetum poeppigii Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Festuco subandinae-Pernettyion poeppigii Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Festuco subandinae-Pernettyetum poeppigii Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Blechno penna-marinae-Pernettyion mucronatae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Blechno penna-marinae-Pernettyetum mucronatae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Empetro rubrum-Pernettyetum mucronatae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Ephedro chilensis-Chuquiragetea oppositifoliae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012b)

Tetraglochini alati-Chuquiragetalia oppositifoliae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012b)

Zoellnerallio andini-Chuquiragion oppositifoliae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012b)

Mutisio acerosae-Chuquiragetum oppositifoliae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012b)

Mutisio acerosae-Mulinetum spinosi Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012b)

Senecio eruciformis-Fabianetum imbricatae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012b)

Berberido empetrifoliae-Chuquiragetum oppositifoliae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012b)

Aldamo revolutae-Guindilietum trinervis Amigo & Flores-Toro 2017 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2017)

Festuco acanthophyllae-Chuquiragetum oppositifoliae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2017 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2017)

Oreopolus glacialis-Pozoa coriacea comm. Amigo & Flores-Toro 2017 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2017)

Haplopappo velutini-Chuquiragetum oppositifoliae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012b)

Gutierrezio paniculatae-Trichoceretea chilensis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Saturejio gilliesii-Puyetalia chilensis Balduzzi, Tomaselli, Serey & Villaseñor 1982 sec. Balduzzi et al. (1982)

Saturejion gilliesii Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Gutierrezio paniculatae-Baccharidetum rosmarinifoliae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Colletio spinosae-Fabianetum imbricatae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Carpobroto aequilateri-Baccharidion macraei Luebert & Muñoz-Schick 2005 sec. Luebert and Muñoz-Schick (2005)

Bahio ambrosioidis-Nolanetum crassifoliae Luebert & Muñoz-Schick 2005 sec. Luebert and Muñoz-Schick (2005)

Margyricarpo pinnati-Chorizantheum vaginatae Luebert & Muñoz-Schick 2005 sec. Luebert and Muñoz-Schick (2005)

Colletio hystricis-Schinatum polygamae Luebert & Muñoz-Schick 2005 sec. Luebert and Muñoz-Schick (2005)

Helianthemetea guttati Rivas Goday et Rivas-Martínez 1963 sec. Deil et al. (2007)

order?

Chaetanthero serratae-Vulpion megaluræ Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Chaetanthero serratae-Vulpium megaluræ Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Crassula closiana-Microseris pygmaea comm. Deil, Alvarez & Paulini 2007 sec. Deil et al. (2007)

Hypochaeris glabra-Leontodon taraxacoides comm. Deil, Alvarez & Paulini 2007 sec. Deil et al. (2007)

Lemnetea minoris Koch & Tüxen ex den Hartog & Segal 1964 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Lemnetalia minoris Koch & Tüxen ex den Hartog & Segal 1964 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Lemnion australis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Lemno gibbae-Azolletum chilense Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Lemno valdivianae-Azolletum filiculoides Steubing, Ramírez & Alberdi 1980 sec. Steubing et al. (1980)

Lemno minutae-Lemnetum gibbae Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Lithraeo causticae-Cryptocaryetea albae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Cryptocaryetalia albae (Schmithüsen 1954) Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Cryptocaryion albae Schmithüsen 1954 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Lucumo valparadisaea-Cryptocaryetum albae (Schmithüsen 1954) Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

= *Lucuma valparadisea* comm. Schmithüsen 1954

Beilschmiedienion miersii Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012a)

Aextoxico punctati-Cryptocaryetum albae Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012a)

Beilschmiedietum miersii Schmithüsen 1954 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012a)

Beilschmiedietum miersii osmorhizetosum berterii Schmithüsen 1954 sec. Schmithüsen (1954)

Beilschmiedietum miersii typicum Schmithüsen 1954 sec. Schmithüsen (1954)

Beilschmiedio miersii-Crinodendretum pataguae Villaseñor & Serey ex Amigo & Flores-Toro 2012 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012a)

- Cryptocaryenion albae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2012a)
- Boldo chilensis-Cryptocaryetum albae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Boldo chilensis-Cryptocaryetum albae typicum* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Boldo chilensis-Cryptocaryetum albae nothofagetosum obliquae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Kageneckio angustifoliae-Quillajion saponariae* Amigo & Flores-Toro 2013 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2013)
- Mutisio latifoliae-Quillajetum saponariae* Amigo & Flores-Toro 2013 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2013)
- Schino montani-Austrocedretum chilensis* Amigo & Flores-Toro 2013 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2013)
- Colliguajo integerrimae-Quillajetum saponariae* Amigo & Flores-Toro 2013 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2013)
- Lithraeion causticae* Schmithüsen 1954 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Lomatium hirsutae-Lithraetum causticae* Amigo, San Martín & Quintanilla 2000 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)
- Azaro dentatae-Lithraetum causticae* Amigo & Flores-Toro 2013 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2013)
- Quillajo saponariae-Lithraetum causticae* (Schmithüsen 1954) Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Jubaeo spectabilis-Lithraetum causticae* Schmithüsen 1954 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Austrocedro chilensis-Lithraetum causticae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Boldo chilensis-Lithraetum causticae* (Schmithüsen 1954) Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- = *Lythraea caustica-Peumus boldus* comm. Schmithüsen 1954
- Acacio cavenis-Cestrion parqui* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Rubo ulmifoliae-Cestretum parqui* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Cestro parqui-Trevoetum trinervae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Azaro gilliesii-Escallonietum berterianae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Littorelletea australis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

order?

alliance?

- Phyla nodiflora* comm. San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)
- Gratiolo peruviana-Littorelletum australis* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Loasetea Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Loasetalia* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Erythraeion chilensis* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Erythraea chilensis* comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Loasion acanthifolii* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Tropaeolo sepciosi-Loasetum acanthifolii* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Abutilo vitifolii-Loasetum acanthifolii* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)**Mayteno boariae-Salicetea humboldtiana** Amigo, Flores-Toro & Caballero-Serrano 2019 sec. Amigo et al. (2019)*Mayteno boariae-Salicetalia humboldtiana* Amigo, Flores-Toro & Caballero-Serrano 2019 sec. Amigo et al. (2019)*Mayteno boariae-Salicion humboldtiana* Amigo, Flores-Toro & Caballero-Serrano 2019 sec. Amigo et al. (2019)*Otholobio glandulosi-Salicetum humboldtiana* Amigo, Flores-Toro & Caballero-Serrano 2019 sec. Amigo et al. (2019)*Baccharido salicifoliae-Myrceugenietum lanceolatae* Amigo, Flores-Toro & Caballero-Serrano 2019 sec. Amigo et al. (2019)*Escallonion illinito-myrtoidae* Amigo, Flores-Toro & Caballero-Serrano 2019 sec. Amigo et al. (2019)*Mayteno boariae-Escallonietum illinitae* Amigo & Flores-Toro 2017 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2017)*Buddlejo globosae-Escallonietum myrtoideae* Amigo & Flores-Toro 2017 sec. Amigo and Flores-Toro (2017)**Molinio caeruleae-Arrhenatheretea elatioris** Tüxen 1937 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Agrostietalia capillaris* San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)*Agrostion chilensis* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Leontodo taraxacoidis-Piptochaetietum montevidense* Ramírez, San Martín, Contreras & San Martín 1994 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)= *Leontodo taraxacoidis-Piptochaetietum montevidense chevruiletosum sarmentosae* Ramírez, San Martín, Contreras & San Martín 1994*Acaeno ovalifoli-Agrostietum castellanae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)= *Acaeno ovalifoli-Agrostietum capillaris* Ramírez, Amigo & San Martín 2003*Acaeno ovalifoli-Agrostietum castellanae typicum* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)*Acaeno ovalifoli-Agrostietum castellanae lotetosum uliginosae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Agrostis tenuis-Holcus lanatus-Lotus uliginosus comm. Montaldo 1975 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)

= *Hypochaeris radicata-Agrostis tenuis* comm. Montaldo 1975

Agrostis capillaris-Lotetum corniculatae Ramírez, San Martín, Ramírez & San Martín 1992 sec. Ramírez et al. (1992)

Trifolium repentis-Vulpium bromoides Ramírez, Amigo & San Martín 2003 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)

= *Junco imbricati-Agrostietum capillaris* Ramírez, Amigo & San Martín 2003

Cynosuro echinati-Agrostietum capillaris Ramírez, Ellies, Mac Donald & Seguel 2003 sec. Ramírez et al. (2003b)

Hyperico perforati-Agrostietum castellanae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

= *Hyperico perforati-Agrostietum capillaris* Ramírez, San Martín, Ellies & Mac Donald 1997

Hyperico perforati-Agrostietum castellanae typicum Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Hyperico perforati-Agrostietum castellanae stipetosum Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Hyperico perforati-Agrostietum castellanae lotetosum uliginosae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Bromo cathartici-Lolienion perennis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Bromo cathartici-Lolietum perennis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Juncion proceri Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)

Mentha pulegium-Juncus procerus comm. Ramírez, San Martín, Contreras & San Martín 1994 sec. Ramírez et al. (1994)

Mentha pulegium-Agrostietum capillaris San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)

Juncetum microcephali San Martín in San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Centello asiatici-Anthoxantheum utriculariae Ramírez, Amigo & San Martín 2003 sec. Ramírez et al. (2003a)

= *Anthoxanthum utriculatum* comm. San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998

Juncetum proceri Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

= *Agrostis tenuis-Juncus procerus* comm. Montaldo 1975

Myrteolo nummulariae-Sphagnetea magellanici Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2017)

Myrteolo-Sphagnetalia magellanici Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2017)

Astelio pumilae-Oreobolion obtusanguli Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2017)

Schoeno andini-Lepidothamnetum fonkii Ramírez et al. 2014 sec. Ramírez et al. (2014a)

- Astelio pumilae-Oreoboletum obtusanguli* San Martín, Ramírez & Figueroa 1999 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)
 = *Astelia pumila* comm. Ramírez 1968
- Schoeno rhynchosporoides-Oreoboletum obtusanguli* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Donatio fascicularis-Schoenetum antarctici* (Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985) Amigo, San Martín, Ramírez & Alvarez 2017 sec. Amigo et al. (2017)
 = *Donatietum fascicularis* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985
 = *Schoeno antarctici-Nothofagetum antarcticae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985
- Chusqueo montano-Schoenoetum antarctici* Ramírez et al. 2014 sec. Ramírez et al. (2014b)
- Donatio fascicularis-Oreoboletum obtusanguli* Ramírez et al. 2014 sec. Ramírez et al. (2014b)
- Drosero uniflorae-Donatietum fascicularis* San Martín, Ramírez & Figueroa 1999 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)
 = *Donatia fascicularis* comm. Ramírez 1968
 = *Marsippospermo philippii-Astelietum pumilae* San Martín, Ramírez & Figueroa 1999
- Gaultherio-Sphagnion magellanicum* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2017)
 = *Sphagnion magellanicum* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985
- Gaultherio-Sphagnetum magellanicum* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)
 = *Sphagnetum magellanicum* Pisano 1977
- Donatio fascicularis-Sphagnetum magellanicum* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Carico nigroglochini-Sphagnetum magellanicum* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Marsippospermetum grandiflori* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Abrotanello linearifoliae-Bolacion caespitosae* Amigo et al. 2017 sec. Amigo et al. (2017)
 = *Bolaco caespitosae-Phyllacnetalia uliginosae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985
 = *Bolaco caespitosae-Phyllacnion uliginosae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985
- Senecio trifurcati-Bolacetum caespitosae* Amigo, San Martín, Ramírez & Alvarez 2017 sec. Amigo et al. (2017)
 = *Bolaco caespitosae-Phyllacnetum uliginosae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985
- Azorello selaginis-Bolacetum caespitosae* Amigo, San Martín, Ramírez & Alvarez 2017 sec. Amigo et al. (2017)
 = *Azorello selaginis-Phyllachnetum uliginosae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985
 = *Astelio pumilae-Phyllachnetum uliginosae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985

= *Lomatium ferrugineae-Dacrydietum fonckii* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985

Cryptochiletum grandiflorae Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Nanojuncetea australis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Nanojuncetalia australis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Juncion planifoli Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Navarretia involucrata comm. prov. sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)

= *Leontodo taraxacoidis-Piptochaetietum montevidense navarretietosum involucratae* Ramírez, San Martín, Contreras & San Martín 1994

Juncetum planifoli Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Anagallis alternifolia-Juncus planifolius comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Scirpo inundati-Limoselletum aquaticae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Eleocharis pachycarpa-Lythrum portula comm. San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)

Nothofagetea pumilionis-antarcticae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

= *Nothofagetea pumilionis* (Oberdorfer 1960) Hildebrand-Vogel, Godoy & Vogel 1990

Adenocaulo chilensis-Nothofagetalia pumilionis (Oberdorfer 1960) Hildebrand-Vogel, Godoy & Vogel 1990 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

= *Pumilietalia* Oberdorfer 1960

Vicio nigrescentis-Nothofagion pumilionis (Hildebrand-Vogel, Godoy & Vogel 1990) Amigo & Rodríguez-Gutián 2015 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

= *Lagenophoro-Nothofagion pumilionis* (Oberdorfer 1960) Freiberg 1985

= *Vicio nigrescentis-Nothofagenion pumilionis* Hildebrand-Vogel, Godoy & Vogel 1990

= *Pumilion* Oberdorfer 1960

Carici lateriflorae-Araucarietum araucanae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Carici lateriflorae-Araucarietum araucanae araucarietosum araucanae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Carici lateriflorae-Araucarietum araucanae drimydetosum andinae Amigo & Rodríguez-Gutián 2015 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Carici lateriflorae-Araucarietum araucanae quinchamaliotosum chilensis (Finckh 1996) Amigo & Rodríguez-Gutián 2015 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Anemone antucensis-Nothofagetum pumilionis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Chilotricho rosmarinifolii-Nothofagetum pumilionis Eskuche 2002 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Nothofagetum antarcticae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Senecioni acanthifolii-Nothofagion pumilionis Amigo & Rodríguez-Gutián 2015 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Macrachaenio gracilis-Nothofagetum pumilionis Eskuche 1973 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Macrachaenio gracilis-Nothofagetum pumilionis ovidietosum andinae Amigo & Rodríguez-Gutián 2015 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Macrachaenio gracilis-Nothofagetum pumilionis chusqueetosum culeou Eskuche 1973 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Berberidi ilicifoliae-Nothofagetum pumilionis Hildebrand-Vogel, Godoy & Vogel 1990 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Senecioni acanthifolii-Nothofagetum pumilionis Eskuche 1973 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Senecioni acanthifolii-Nothofagetum pumilionis gunneretosum magellanicae Villagrán 1980 ex Amigo & Rodríguez-Gutián 2015 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Viola magellanicae-Nothofagetalia pumilionis (Roig et al. 1985) Hildebrand-Vogel, Godoy & Vogel 1990 sec. Amigo and Rodríguez-Gutián (2015)

Opuntietea sphaericae Galán de Mera & Vicente Orellana 1996 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Atriplicetalia imbricatae Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Ambrosio artemisioidis-Atriplicion imbricatae Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Acantholippio deserticolae-Atriplicetum imbricatae Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Oreocereo leucotrichi-Neoraimondietalia arequipensis Galán de Mera & Vicente Orellana 1996 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Corryocaction brevistyli Galán de Mera & Vicente Orellana 1996 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Oreocereo leucotrichi-Ambrosietum artemisioidis Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Parastrephio lepidophyllae-Fabianetea densae Rivas-Martínez & Navarro in Navarro & Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Parastrephietalia lepidophyllae Navarro 1993 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Diplostephio meyenii-Fabianion ramulosae Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Lophopappetum tarapacani Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Diplostephio meyenii-Fabianetum ramulosae Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Parastrephion lepidophyllae Navarro 1993 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Parastrephietum lepidophyllo-quadrangulare Navarro in Navarro & Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Lobivio ferocis-Fabianion densae Ruthsatz ex G. Navarro 1993 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Festucion orthophyllae Ruthsatz 1977 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Azorello compactae-Festucion orthophyllae Galán de Mera, Cáceres & González 2003 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Wernerio aretioidis-Parastrephietum lucidae Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Anthobryo triandri-Parastrephietum lucidae Navarro in Navarro & Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Deyeuxio curvulae-Wernerietum incisae Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Fabianion stephanii Galán de Mera, Cáceres & González 2003 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Fabiano bryoidis-Stipetalia frigidae Navarro in Navarro & Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Urbanio pappigerae-Stipion frigidae Navarro 1993 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)
Adesmio melanthis-Artemisietum copae Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)
Fabiano bryoidis-Adesmietum erinaceae Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)
Adesmietum frigidum-echinoris Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)
Mulino crassifolii-Deyeuxietum crispae Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)
Stipo frigidae-Adesmietum caespitosae Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)
Nicotianetum petunioidis Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)
Senecionetum chrysolepidis Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)

Phragmito-Magnocaricetea Klika in Klika & Novák 1941 sec. Mucina (1997)

= *Phragmitetea communis* Tüxen et Preising 1942

Gynerio-Bambusetalia Borhidi in Borhidi, Muñiz & Del Risco (1979) 1983 sec. Galán de Mera et al. (2003)

Cortaderion jubatae Galán de Mera, Cáceres & González 2003 sec. Galán de Mera et al. (2003)

Cortaderia atacamensis comm. Ackermann 2001 sec. Ackermann (2001)

order? sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)

= *Jussiaeetea repentis* Oberdorfer 1960

Ludwigion peploides San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

- Ludwigia peploides-Sagittaria montevidense* comm. San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)
- Polygono hydropiperoides-Jussiaetum repentis* Steubing, Ramírez & Alberdi 1980 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)
- = *Jussiaea repens* comm. Oberdorfer 1960
- = *Polygono hydropiperoides-Ludwigietum peploides* (Steubing, Ramírez & Alberdi 1980) San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993
- Glycerietum multiflorae* Contreras et al. in San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)
- Gnaphalio cymatoidis-Polygonetum hydropiperoides* San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)
- Scirpietalia californici* San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)
- Scirpion californici* San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)
- Sagittario montevidensis-Alismetum plantago-aquaticae* Steubing, Ramírez & Alberdi 1980 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)
- = *Alismo plantago-aquaticae-Sagittarietum montevidensis* San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993
- Scirpetum californici* (Añazco 1978) Añazco, Moraga & Ramírez 1981 sec. Añazco et al. (1981)
- Cyperetalia eragrostis* San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)
- Cyperion eragrostis* San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)
- Loto uliginosi-Cyperetum eragrostis* San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)
- Eleocharietum macrostachyae* San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)
- Eleocharietum pachycarpae* San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)
- Junco proceri-Caricetum ripariae* San Martín in San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)

Plantaginetea majoris Tüxen et Preising ex Tüxen 1950 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

- Plantaginetalia majoris* Tüxen 1950 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Polygonion avicularis* Braun-Blanquet 1931 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Malvo parviflorae-Polygonetum avicularis* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Solivo valdivianae-Plantaginetum majoris* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Solivo valdivianae-Plantaginetum majoris typicum* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Solivo valdivianae-Plantaginetum majoris lepidietosum spicati* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Solivo valdivianae-Plantaginetum majoris juncetosum imbricati* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Sagino procumbentis-Bryetum argentei Diéumont, Sissingh & Westhoff 1940 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Agropyro-Rumicion crispi Nordhagen 1940 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Paspalo distichi-Agrostietum semiverticillatae Braun-Blanquet 1936 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Galega officinalis comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Rumici-Menthetum rotundifolii Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Plantagini rigidae-Distichietea muscoidis Rivas-Martínez & Tovar 1982 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Calamagrostio jamesonii-Distichietalia muscoidis Rivas-Martínez & Tovar 1982 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Calamagrostio jamesonii-Distichion muscoidi Rivas-Martínez & Tovar 1982 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Hypselo reniformis-Plantaginion rigidae Rivas-Martínez & Tovar 1982 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Calamagrostietalia nitidulae Galán de Mera, Cáceres & González 2003 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Calamagrostion chrysanthae Rivas-Martínez & Tovar 1982 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Puccinellio frigidiae-Calamagrostietum eminentis Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)

Plantaginetalia tubulosae Gutte 1985 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Oxychloion andinae Ruthsatz 1995 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Oxychloetum andinae Ruthsatz 1995 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)

Hypselo reniformis-Plantaginion tubulosae Galán de Mera, Cáceres & González 2003 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Wernerion pygmaeae Ruthsatz 1977 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Lycion humilis Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Lycietum humilis Luebert & Gajardo 2000 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2000)

Polylepidetea tarapacano-besseri Rivas-Martínez & G. Navarro in G. Navarro & M. Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Polylepidetalia tarapacano-besseri G. Navarro in G. Navarro & M. Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Polylepidion incano-besseri G. Navarro in G. Navarro & M. Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Polylepidion tomentello-tarapacanae G. Navarro in G. Navarro & M. Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Chuquirago rotundifoliae-Polylepidetum rugulosae (Galán de Mera, Cáceres & González 2003) Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Mutisio lanigerae-Polylepidetum tarapacanae Navarro in Navarro & Maldonado 2002 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Potametea Klika ex Klika & Novák 1941 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Magnopotametalia den Hartog & Segal 1964 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Magnopotamion (Vollmar 1947) den Hartog & Segal 1964 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Potametum luscentis Hueck 1931 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Nymphaeeion albae Oberdorfer 1957 sec. den Hartog and Segal (1964)

Myriophyllo aquatica-Potametum linguatus Barrera & Ramírez in San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Utriculario gibbae-Nymphaeetum albae Barrera & Ramírez in San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Parvopotametalia den Hartog & Segal 1964 sec. den Hartog and Segal (1964)

Parvopotamion (Vollmar 1947) den Hartog & Segal 1964 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Potamogeton pusillus comm. San Martín, Ramírez & Ojeda 1998 sec. San Martín et al. (1998)

Egerietum densae Steubing, Ramírez & Alberdi 1980 sec. Steubing et al. (1980)

Myriophylletum aquatici Medina in San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993 sec. San Martín et al. (1993)

Callitrichetum stagnalis-chilensis Steubing, Ramírez & Alberdi 1980 sec. Steubing et al. (1980)

Myriophyllum aquaticum-Potamogeton filiformis comm. Luebert & Gajardo 2005 sec. Luebert and Gajardo (2005)

Rostkovieta magellanicae Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Rostkovietalia magellanicae Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Rostkovion magellanicae Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Rostkovietum magellanicae Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Ranunculo trullifolii-Rostkovietum magellanicae Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Scirpo californici-Drepanocladetum Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)

Senecionetea chilensis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

order?

alliance?

Poa vulcanica comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Agrostis leptotrichae-Senecionetum chilensis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Festucetum subandinae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Stellarietea mediae Tüxen ex von Rochow 1951 sec. Mucina (1997)

= *Chenopodietea* Braun-Blanquet 1951

Chenopodietalia muralis Braun-Blanquet 1936 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

alliance?

Atriplici semibaccatae-Chenopodietum zobellii Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Chenopodietum muralis Braun-Blanquet et Maire 1924 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Chenopodietum muralis typicum Braun-Blanquet et Maire 1924 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Chenopodietum muralis xanthetosum spinosum Braun-Blanquet et Maire 1924 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Carduo pychnocephali-Conietum maculati Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Oxybapho micranthi-Hordeetum murinum Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Oxybapho micranthi-Hordeetum murinum typicum Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Oxybapho micranthi-Hordeetum murinum carduetosum pychnocephali Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Silybo mariani-Cynaretum cardunculi Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Polygono persicariae-Chenopodietalia albi Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Polygono persicariae-Chenopodion albi Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Setario verticillatae-Euphorbietum pepli Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Spergula arvensis comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Soncho asperi-Euphorbietum pepli Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

order? sec. Alvarez and Luebert (2022)

= *Secalietea* Braun-Blanquet 1951

alliance?

Meliloto officinalis-Avenetum fatuae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Viola tricoloris-Avenetum fatuae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Onopordetalia acanthi Braun-Blanquet & Tüxen 1943 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

alliance?

Sisymbrio officinalis-Cirsietum vulgaris Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Polygono persicariae-Conietum maculati Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Rumicetum chilensis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Chenopodietalia albi Tüxen & Lohmeyer 1943 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

alliance?

Malva neglecta comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Chenopodium album comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Sisymbrio officinalis-Hordeetum murinum Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Tessario integrifoliae-Baccharidetea salicifoliae Rivas-Martínez & Navarro in Navarro & Maldonado 2002 sec. Amigo et al. (2019)

= *Salicetea chilena* Oberdorfer 1960

order?

alliance?

Tessario absinthioides-Baccharidetum marginalis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

Wintero-Nothofagetea Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)

Laurelietalia philippiana Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

= *Wintero-Nothofagetalia* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985

Nothofago-Eucryphon cordifoliae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)

Nothofagenion glauco-alessandri Amigo, San Martín & Quintanilla 2000 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)

Bomareo salsillae-Nothofagetum glaucae Amigo, San Martín & Quintanilla 2000 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)

Nothofagetum alessandri San Martín, Figueroa & Ramírez 1984 sec. San Martín et al. (1984)

Aextoxiconenion punctati Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

- Nothofago obliquae-Perseetum lingue* Oberdorfer & Schmithüsen ex Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Nothofago obliquae-Perseetum lingue typicum Oberdorfer & Schmithüsen ex Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Nothofago obliquae-Perseetum lingue boldetosum Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Lapagerio roseae-Aextoxiconetum punctati Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Peperomio-Aextoxiconetum punctati (Muñoz & Pisano) Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Nothofago dombeyi-Eucryphienion cordifoliae (Oberdorfer 1960) Amigo, San Martín & Quintanilla 2000 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)
= *Dombeyo-Eucryphenion cordifoliae* Oberdorfer 1960
= *Nothofagenion alpinae-procerae* Oberdorfer 1960
Nothofago dombeyi-Eucryphietum cordifoliae (Oberdorfer 1960) Amigo, San Martín & Quintanilla 2000 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)
= *Dombeyo-Eucryphietum cordifoliae* Oberdorfer 1960
= *Dombeyo-Eucryphietum cordifoliae typicum* Oberdorfer 1960
= *Dombeyo-Eucryphietum cordifoliae saxegothaeetosum conspicuae* Oberdorfer 1960
= *Dombeyo-Eucryphietum cordifoliae pernettyetosum poeppigii* Oberdorfer 1960
Nothofagetum procerae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Nothofago procerae-Dasyphyllletum diacanthoides Frank & Finckh in Finckh 1996 sec. Finckh (1996)
Elymo andini-Nothofagenion obliquae (Oberdorfer 1960) San Martín, Figueroa & Ramírez 1984 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)
= *Elymo andini-Nothofagion obliquae* Oberdorfer 1960
Elymo andini-Nothofagetum obliquae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Nothofago-Winterion Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Weinmannienion trichospermae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Luzuriago marginatae-Nothofagetum nitidae Ramírez et al. 2014 sec. Ramírez et al. (2014a)
Luzuriago polyphyllae-Nothofagetum nitidae Amigo, Ramírez & Quintanilla 2004 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
Laurelio philippiana-Weinmannietum trichospermae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Pilgerodendronetum uviferi Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
Desfontainio fulgens-Tepualietum stipularis Ramírez et al. 2014 sec. Ramírez et al. (2014a)
Fitzroyetum cupressoidis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)

- Laurelio philippiana*-*Nothofagion dombeyi* Pollmann 2001 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
- Nothofagion betuloidis* (Oberdorfer 1960) Amigo, San Martín & Quintanilla 2000 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)
= *Nothofagion betuloidis* Oberdorfer 1960
- Nothofagetum betuloidis* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
- Nothofagetum betuloidis typicum* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Nothofagetum betuloidis escallonietosum serratae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Nothofagetum betuloidis tepualietosum stipularis* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Nothofagetum betuloidis pseudopnaetosum laetevirentis* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Hebo ellipticae*-*Pernettyetum mucronatae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Embothrio coccineo*-*Nothofagion betuloidis* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Embothrio coccineo*-*Nothofagetum betuloidis* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Lomatium ferrugineae*-*Nothofagetum betuloidis* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Baccharido nivalis*-*Nothofagetum betuloidis* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Acaeno magellanicae*-*Gunnerion magellanicae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Ribo magellanici*-*Pernettyetum mucronatae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Ribo magellanici*-*Pernettyetum mucronatae typicum* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Ribo magellanici*-*Pernettyetum mucronatae nothofagetosum antarcticae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Acaeno magellanicae*-*Gunneretum magellanicae* Roig, Dollenz & Méndez 1985 sec. Roig et al. (1985)
- Berberido trigonae*-*Nothofagetalia dombeyi* Pollmann 2001 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
- Austrocedro chilensis*-*Nothofagion dombeyi* Eskuche 1968 sec. Amigo et al. (2010)
- Nothofago obliquae*-*Prumnopitydetum andinae* Amigo, Rodríguez-Gutián & Ramírez 2010 sec. Amigo et al. (2010)
- Orito myrtoidei*-*Austrocedretum chilensis* Amigo 2019 sec. Amigo (2019)
- Myrceugenio*-*Nothofagion dombeyi* (Eskuche 1999) Pollmann 2001 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
- Chrysosplenio valdivici*-*Nothofagetum dombeyi* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
- Myrceugenietalia exsuccae* (Oberdorfer 1960) Amigo, San Martín & Quintanilla 2000 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)
= *Palud-Myrceugenietalia exsuccae* Oberdorfer 1960

- Myrceugenion exsuccae* Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
 Temo divaricati-Myrceugenietum exsuccae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
 = *Blepharocalyco cruckshanksii-Myrceugenietum exsuccae* San Martín, Medina, Ojeda & Ramírez 1993
 Drymido winteri-Myrceugenietum exsuccae Villagrán 1980 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)
 Myrceugenelletum apiculatae Villagrán 1980 sec. Amigo et al. (2000)
- Aristotelienea chilensis* Amigo, Ramírez & Quintanilla 2007 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
Aristotelietalia chilensis (Oberdorfer 1960) Hildebrand 1983 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
= *Berberidetalia austro-americanae* Oberdorfer 1960
 Berberidion buxifoliae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
 Rhaphithamno spinosi-Aristotelietum chilensis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
 Rhaphithamno spinosi-Aristotelietum chilensis peumetosum boldi Amigo, Ramírez & Quintanilla 2007 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
 Rhaphithamno spinosi-Aristotelietum chilensis typicum Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
 Alstroemerio aurantiacae-Aristotelietum chilensis Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
 Azaro microphyllae-Aristotelietum chilensis Amigo, Ramírez & Quintanilla 2007 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
 Ulex europaeus comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
 Berberis buxifolia comm. Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
 Fuchsia magellanicae-Chusqueetum quillae Hildebrand 1983 sec. Hildebrand (1983)
- Fuchsia magellanicae-Amomyrtion lumae* Amigo, Ramírez & Quintanilla 2007 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
 Lomatium ferruginae-Amomyrtetum lumae Amigo, Ramírez & Quintanilla 2007 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
 Aristotelio chilensis-Fuchsietum magellanicae Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Oberdorfer (1960)
 Aristotelio chilensis-Fuchsietum magellanicae amomyrtetosum lumae Amigo, Ramírez & Quintanilla 2007 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
 Aristotelio chilensis-Fuchsietum magellanicae typicum Oberdorfer 1960 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
 Escallonio alpinae-Fuchsietum magellanicae Amigo, Ramírez & Quintanilla 2007 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
- Escallonion rubrae* Eskuche 1969 sec. Amigo et al. (2007)
Baccharido linearidis-Discarion articulatae Eskuche 1969 sec. Amigo (2019)
 Fabiano imbricatae-Discarietum articulatae Amigo 2019 sec. Amigo (2019)

Discarietum articulatae Eskuche 1969 sec. Amigo (2019)

Syntaxon Views

- Ackermann M (2001) Die Vegetation der Bachflüße in der Hochatacama (II. Region) in Chile. Candidate thesis. Philipps-Universität Marburg
- Alvarez M, Luebert F (2022) This publication.
- Amigo J (2019) A forest community of biogeographical interest: The cypress woodland of the Antuco Volcano (Bío-Bío Region, Chile). *International Journal of Geobotanical Research*.
- Amigo J, San Martín C, Ramírez C, Alvarez M (2017) Nomenclatural revision and syntaxonomical proposal for wetland peat vegetation in the Valdivian-Magellanian Region. *Lazaroa* 38: 165–187. <https://doi.org/10.5209/laza.56343>
- Amigo J, Flores-Toro L, Caballero-Serrano V (2019) Riparian or phreatophile woodland and shrubland vegetation in the Central Chilean biogeographic region: Phytosociological study. *Mediterranean Botany* 40: 243–258. <https://doi.org/10.5209/mbot.63049>
- Amigo J, Flores-Toro L (2012a) Revisión sintaxonómica de los bosques esclerófilos de Chile Central: La alianza *Cryptocaryon albae*. *Lazaroa* 33: 171–196. https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_laza.2012.v33.40283
- Amigo J, Flores-Toro L (2012b) The supramediterranean scrub in the central Chilean province: Phytosociological position. *International Journal of Geobotanical Research* 2: 87–110.
- Amigo J, Flores-Toro L (2013) A new contribution to syntaxonomy of sclerophyllous forests and pre-forests of Central Chile: *Lithraeion causticae* alliance. *International Journal of Geobotanical Research* 3: 47–67.
- Amigo J, Flores-Toro L (2017) Contribution to the syntaxonomy of the supramediterranean shrubby vegetation of Central Chile. *International Journal of Geobotanical Research*.
- Amigo J, San Martín J, Quintanilla LG (2000) Estudio fitosociológico de los bosques de *Nothofagus glauca* (Phil.) Krasser del Centro-Sur de Chile. *Phytocoenologia* 30: 193–221.
- Amigo J, Ramírez C, Quintanilla LG (2007) Mantle communities of the temperate woodlands of South Central Chile: A phytosociological study of the order *aristotelietales chilensis*. *Phytocoenologia* 37: 269–319. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0340-269x/2007/0037-0269>
- Amigo J, Rodríguez Guitián MA, Ramírez C (2010) The lleuque forests of South Central Chile: A phytosociological study and syntaxonomical classification within South American temperate forests. *Lazaroa* 31: 85–98.
- Amigo J, Rodríguez-Guitián MA (2015) Syntaxonomical review of sub-Antarctic orotemperate forests (*Adenocaulo chilensis-Nothofagetalia pumilionis*) in the Valdivian biogeographic province. *International Journal of Geobotanical Research* 5: 13–35.
- Añazco N, Moraga M, Ramírez C (1981) Distribución de comunidades pratenses antropogénicas en un gradiente de inclinación en Valdivia, Chile. *Agro Sur* 9: 14–27.
- Balduzzi A, Tomaselli R, Serey I, Villaseñor R (1982) Degradation of the mediterranean type of vegetatin in central chile. *Ecol Medit* 8: 223–240.
- Deil U, Alvarez M, Paulini I (2007) Native and non-native species in annual grassland vegetation in Mediterranean Chile. *Phytocoenologia* 37: 769–784. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0340-269x/2007/0037-0769>
- den Hartog C, Segal S (1964) A new classification of the water-plant communities. *Acta Bot Neerl* 13: 367–393. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1438-8677.1964.tb00163.x>
- Finckh M (1996) Die Wälder des Villarica-Nationalparks (Südchile) – Lebensgemeinschaften als Grundlage für ein Schutzkonzept. 181 pp.
- Galán de Mera A, Cáceres C, González A (2003) La vegetación de la alta montaña andina del sur del Perú. *Acta Botanica Malacitana* 28: 121–147.
- Hildebrand R (1983) Die Vegetation der Tieflandsgebüsche des südchilenischen Lorbeerwaldgebiets unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der Neophytenproblematik. *Phytocoenologia* 11: 145–223. <https://doi.org/10.1127/phyto/11/1983/145>
- Kohler A (1970) Geobotanische Untersuchungen an Küstendünen Chiles zwischen 27 und 42 Grad südlicher Breite. *Botanische Jahrbücher für Systematik, Pflanzengeschichte und Pflanzengeographie* 90: 55–200.
- Luebert F, Gajardo R (2000) Vegetación de los Andes áridos del norte de Chile. *Lazaroa* 21: 111–130.

- Luebert F, Gajardo R (2005) Vegetación alto andina de Parinacota (norte de Chile) y una sinopsis de la vegetación de la Puna meridional. *Phytocoenologia* 35: 79–128. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0340-269X/2005/0035-0079>
- Luebert F, Muñoz-Schick M (2005) Contribución al conocimiento de la flora y vegetación de las dunas de Concón. *Boletín del Museo Nacional de Historia Natural, Chile* 54: 11–35.
- Mucina L (1997) Conspectus of classes of European vegetation. *Folia Geobotanica et Phytotaxonomica* 32: 117–172.
- Oberdorfer E (1960) *Pflanzensoziologische Studien in Chile*. J. Cramer, Weinheim, 208 pp.
- Ramírez C, Ortiz I, San Martín C, Vidal OJ, Alvarez M, Pérez Y, Solís JL, Alvarez I (2014a) Estudio preliminar de la biodiversidad vegetal terrestre en el Estero Walker (Región de Aysén, Chile): Utilizando líneas base de proyectos de inversión. *Gayana Botánica* 71: 227–245.
- Ramírez C, Amigo J, San Martín C (2003a) Vegetación pratense litoral y dinámica vegetacional antropogénica en Valdivia, Chile. *Agro Sur* 31: 24–37.
- Ramírez C, San Martín C, Ramírez JC, San Martín J (1992) Estudio sinecológico de las praderas del valle del curso inferior del río Imperial (Cautín, Chile). *Ciencia e Investigación Agraria* 19: 97–112.
- Ramírez C, San Martín C, Contreras D, San Martín J (1994) Estudio fitosociológico de la vegetación pratense del valle del río Chol-Chol (Cautín, Chile). *Agro Sur* 22: 41–56.
- Ramírez C, Ellies A, Mac Donald R, Seguel O (2003b) Cambios en la flora y la materia orgánica desde bosques nativos a praderas antropogénicas en suelos volcánicos de la IX Región de Chile. *Revista de la Ciencia del Suelo y Nutrición Vegetal* 3: 1–12.
- Ramírez C, San Martín C, Vidal OJ, Pérez Y, Valenzuela J, Solís JL, Toledo G (2014b) Tundra subantártica en la Isla Grande de Chiloé, Chile: Flora y vegetación turbosa de campañas. *Anales Instituto Patagonia* 42: 17–37.
- Roig FA, Dollenz O, Méndez E (1985) Las comunidades vegetales de la transecta botánica de la Patagonia Austral. Segunda parte: La vegetación en los canales. In: Boelcke O, Moore DM, Roig FA (Eds), *Transecta botánica de la patagonia austral*. Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (Argentina), Instituto de la Patagonia (Chile), Royal Society (Gran Bretaña), Buenos Aires, 457–519.
- San Martín C, Ramírez C, Ojeda P (1998) La vegetación de lagunas primaverales en las cercanías de Temuco (Cautín, Chile). *Acta Botanica Malacitana* 23: 99–120.
- San Martín C, Medina R, Ojeda P, Ramírez C (1993) La biodiversidad vegetacional del Santuario de la Naturaleza "Río Cruces" (Valdivia, Chile). *Acta Botanica Malacitana* 18: 259–279.
- San Martín J, Figueroa H, Ramírez C (1984) Fitosociología de los bosques de ruil (*Nothofagus alessandri* Espinosa) en Chile central. *Revista Chilena de Historia Natural* 57: 171–200.
- Schmithüsen J (1954) *Waldgesellschaften des nördlichen Mittelchile*. *Vegetatio* 5-6: 479–486.
- Steubing L, Ramírez C, Alberdi M (1980) Energy content of water- and bog-plant associations in the Region of Valdivia (Chile). *Vegetatio* 43: 413–161.